

1 **Universal Behavior in the Mesoscale Properties of Amyloid**
2 **Fibrils.**

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Abstract

Amyloid fibrils are ubiquitous proteinaceous aggregates occurring in vivo and in vitro, with an invariant structural fingerprint at the molecular length scale. However, interpretation of their mesoscopic architectures is complicated by diverse observable polymorphic states. We here present a constitutive model for amyloid fibrils based on the minimization of the total energy per fibril. The model is benchmarked on real amyloid fibrils studied by atomic force microscopy. We use multistranded β -lactoglobulin amyloid fibrils as a model system exhibiting a rich polymorphism. The constitutive model quantitatively recapitulates the main mesoscopic topological features of amyloid fibrils, that is, the evolution of fibril periodicity as a function of the ionic strength of the solution and of the fibril width. A universal mesoscopic structural signature of the fibrils emerges from this picture, predicting a general, parameter-free law for the periodicity of the fibrils, that depends solely on the number of protofilaments per fibril. These predictions are validated experimentally and conclusively highlight the role of competing electrostatic and elastic contributions as the main players in the establishment of amyloid fibrils structure.

14 Amyloid fibrils are attracting attention from disciplines as diverse as structural biology,
15 medicine, chemistry, physics, and materials science, not only because of the relevance of these
16 protein aggregates in neurodegenerative diseases [1–4], biotechnology [5], and nanotechnol-
17 ogy [6, 7], but also owing to their uncommon set of physical and structural properties [8–11].
18 These systems share common structural features at the 4–5 Å and 10–11 Å length scales,
19 independently of the specific peptidic primary sequence composing them [12–14]. At larger
20 length scales, however, their forms of polymorphism diverge [15–18], as does the view on the
21 main physical mechanisms ruling amyloid mesoscopic structure [19–26]. It is the structural
22 architecture at these length scales that controls some of the ensemble physical properties,
23 ranging from their persistence length to their liquid crystalline properties in three and two
24 dimensions [27]. These features are epitomized by the existence of a very regular structure in
25 amyloid fibrils at a length scale on the order of tens to hundreds of nanometers [15–18, 28].
26 For example, Adamcik et al. [28] have performed a detailed statistical analysis of atomic
27 force microscopy (AFM) images of fibrils produced in vitro starting from β -lactoglobulin
28 (β lg) monomers, finding that they are organized as twisted ribbons formed by laterally

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29 attaching single protofilaments, and that different populations of fibrils can be identified
30 depending on the number of protofilaments composing them.

31 As pointed out in Ref. [28], the twisting structure of amyloid fibrils may be due to
32 the competing interplay between elasticity and electrostatic repulsion: a ribbonlike packing
33 arrangement of charged protofilaments can lower its electrostatic energy at the nanometer
34 length scale only by twisting around its longitudinal axis. In this way, local like charges
35 close to each other on the fibril increase their mutual distance. On the other hand, greater
36 distances between consecutive segments of the protofilaments are penalized by elastic en-
37 ergy, which favors instead a flat structure, as relaxed as possible. The net result is a twisted
38 morphology, observed in experiments, that emerges as a compromise between the two com-
39 peting, attractive and repulsive, forces. A first experimental and theoretical account of
40 the trade-off between electrostatic and mechanical energies in the establishment of amy-
41 loid fibrils structure was proposed in a subsequent work [29], where preformed β lg fibrils
42 were studied in environments with different salinity. There, it was found that for higher
43 salt concentrations, corresponding to a stronger screening of the Coulomb interactions, the
44 twist was less pronounced, hinting at the crucial role of electrostatics for the twisted ribbon
45 morphology.

46 In the present work, we introduce an original model where the implementation of the
47 subtle interplay between elasticity and electrostatics not only allows a faithful mapping of
48 the amyloids structural features, but also highlights, for the first time, a common universal
49 behavior in their mesoscopic topological signature. We benchmark the structural predic-
50 tions of the model on amyloid fibrils based on multistranded β lg twisted ribbons, which
51 are a perfect model system offering a rich polymorphism of shapes and number of protofil-
52 aments per individual fibrils. The structural features of the fibrils are studied by AFM as
53 a function of the number of constituent protofilaments per fibril, at varying ionic strength
54 (salt concentration), and adsorbed on different surfaces.

55 As shown in Fig. 1(a), each protofilament in the ribbon (represented in the figure as
56 a continuous strand) is modeled as a chain of beads of diameter b connected by springs
57 having center-to-center equilibrium distance $b(1 + \epsilon)$, with $\epsilon > 0$. The numerical value of b
58 is obtained directly from experiments as the height of individually adsorbed protofilaments,
59 and is set to 2 nm [28]. Within our coarse-grained picture, the springs embody the elastic
60 part of the energy, while the electrostatic interaction is accounted for by assigning a charge

61 ze to each bead (e being the electron charge, and z the number of charges on the bead).
 62 A n -stranded ribbon is formed by laterally associating n chains, so that transverse layers
 63 of beads are formed [one such layer is highlighted in Fig. 1(a)]. The final structure is
 64 then obtained by twisting the ribbon around its longitudinal axis, as shown in Fig. 1(a)
 65 for a $n = 5$ fiber (the final structures for $n = 2, 3$ and 4 are also shown in Fig. S1 in the
 66 Supplemental Material). In what follows, we assume each layer not to bend upon twisting,
 67 so to store elastic energy primarily by torsion and not bending. Moreover, in the present
 68 model only interactions between consecutive beads within the same protofilament are taken
 69 into account. This is a reasonable assumption because b is of the same order of the typical
 70 values of the screening length in aqueous solutions, so that electrostatic interactions are
 71 negligible between nonadjacent layers.

72 Because of the geometrical constraints and of the simultaneous action of the two compet-
 73 ing forces, we expect at equilibrium that two consecutive layers will be tilted with respect
 74 to each other by a certain angle ϕ^* , which is assumed to be constant along the ribbon and
 75 small. Since all energy terms in our derivation do not prefer any particular local handed-
 76 ness of the twist, the interaction energy is an even function of the twist angle, so that its
 77 expected shape is that of a double well, which is sketched in Fig. 1(b). Nevertheless, the
 78 fibrils do show a uniform left handedness over the full fibril length [28, 29], which means that
 79 a symmetry-breaking mechanism is at work, imposing an effective chirality on the system.
 80 In what follows, we postulate this intrinsic feature to be responsible for giving a definite
 81 handedness, but to play a negligible role for all other purposes.

82 The (still unknown) small value of ϕ^* allows us to set up a perturbative scheme to compute
 83 the energy of the full fibril, which eventually leads to a very powerful formula for the half-
 84 pitch L . To this aim, let us consider two consecutive layers on the fibril. As mentioned above,
 85 assuming chirality not to play a relevant role in quantitatively determining the twist of the
 86 ribbon, the total (elastic + electrostatic) interaction energy between two consecutive layers
 87 $V_I^r(\phi)$ (where the subscript stresses its dependence on the ionic strength I of the solution)
 88 is expected to be an even function of the angle ϕ , so that the point $\phi = 0$ is stationary (i.e.,
 89 maximum or minimum). However, such an equilibrium point corresponds to an unstable
 90 configuration. Indeed, the $\phi = 0$ state coincides with a perfectly relaxed ribbon, which
 91 must still choose the twisting handedness as driven by chirality. Now, let $U_I(x)$ be the total
 92 interaction energy between two beads having a distance equal to $x + b(1 + \epsilon)$ [we will refer

FIG. 1. (a) Ideal steps leading to the coarse-grained picture of a fibril. A single protofilament (top left) is represented by a chain of beads (top right). Several preformed protofilaments associate laterally (middle left) and the whole structure is subsequently twisted around its longitudinal axis (bottom left), thus obtaining the final fibril. Accordingly, in our model a suitable number of chains are attached to each other (middle right) and homogeneously twisted (bottom right), with consecutive transverse layers tilted by a certain angle ϕ . (b) Left: the variable x is defined as the displacement of the distance between two consecutive beads with respect to the untwisted case. Right: due to the competition between elasticity and the repulsive electrostatic interaction, the interaction energy between two consecutive layers as a function of ϕ has a double-well shape, where the minima $\pm\phi^*$ are obtained as a compromise between a perfectly relaxed ($\phi = 0$) and a strongly twisted ($\phi = \pi/2$) conformation.

93 to x as displacement; see inset in Fig. 1(a)]. If we denote by $x_i(\phi)$ the displacement of the
 94 distance between two beads on the i th protofilament belonging to two consecutive layers
 95 tilted by ϕ , by definition we have

$$V_I^r(\phi) = \sum_i U_I[x_i(\phi)]. \quad (1)$$

96 Since we assumed ϕ to be small, the distance x_i is expected to be very small when compared
 97 to the spring equilibrium distance $b(1+\epsilon)$: $x_i \ll b(1+\epsilon)$. Therefore, we can perform a second-
 98 order Taylor expansion of the right-hand side of Eq. (1), which after some manipulations
 99 gives a formula for $V_I^r(\phi)$ with an explicit dependence on the number of protofilaments n
 100 and, by means of the derivatives $U_I'(0), U_I''(0)$, on the ionic strength I (see Sec. S2 for the

101 detailed derivation),

$$V_I^r(\phi) = \frac{n(n^2 - 1)b}{24(1 + \epsilon)} \left[U_I'(0)\phi^2 + \frac{3n^2 - 7bU_I''(0)}{80} \frac{1 + \epsilon}{1 + \epsilon} \phi^4 \right]$$

102 As we anticipated, within our assumptions the potential is an even function of the angle
 103 ϕ . By minimizing $V_I^r(\phi)$ with respect to ϕ , we end up with a third-degree equation, whose
 104 solutions are $\phi = 0$ and $\phi = \pm\phi^*$, where

$$\phi^* = \sqrt{-\frac{40}{3n^2 - 7} \frac{U_I'(0)}{U_I''(0)} \frac{1 + \epsilon}{b}}. \quad (2)$$

105 We note that, because of the simultaneous presence of the attractive elastic term and the
 106 electrostatic repulsion, the function $U_I(x)$ is expected to present a single minimum for some
 107 $0 < x \ll b(1 + \epsilon)$, so that $U_I'(0) < 0$ and $U_I''(0) > 0$. As a consequence, by computing
 108 the second derivative of $V_I^r(\phi)$ we find that the stationary points found above correspond
 109 respectively to a maximum $\phi = 0$ and two minima ($\phi = \pm\phi^*$), as we had already antici-
 110 pated by physical arguments, so that the stable equilibrium point is given by the minimum
 111 corresponding to the correct chirality. By collecting all the n -independent terms in Eq. (2),
 112 ϕ^* can be rewritten as $\phi^* = A(3n^2 - 7)^{-1/2}$, where the constant A depends on the ionic
 113 strength I of the solution, on the elastic properties, and on the basic geometrical features
 114 of the system (b and ϵ) at the level of single beads. Instead, the n -dependent factor keeps
 115 track of the mesoscopic features of the fibrils, namely the number of protofilaments and
 116 their geometrical arrangement. In other words, our model leads to a net separation of the
 117 properties of the system at the micro- and mesoscale, which enter into ϕ^* as two independent
 118 factors. Finally, the half-pitch L of the fibril is obtained by computing how many layers are
 119 necessary to accumulate a π twisting angle,

$$L = b(1 + \epsilon) \frac{\pi}{A} (3n^2 - 7)^{1/2}. \quad (3)$$

120 The mathematical expression for L leads to some new important insight in the mesoscopic
 121 structure of fibrils. Indeed, because the details of the electrostatic and elastic interactions
 122 are concealed in the multiplicative n -independent quantity A , the ratio between half-pitches
 123 of fibrils composed of different numbers n_2 and n_1 of protofilaments depends only on n_1 and
 124 n_2 ,

$$\frac{L(n_2, I)}{L(n_1, I)} = \sqrt{\frac{3n_2^2 - 7}{3n_1^2 - 7}}, \quad (4)$$

FIG. 2. Left: AFM images of fibrils composed of a different number of protofilaments (A,B,C,D correspond respectively to $n = 2, 3, 4, 5$), incubated on a 10 mM solution and adsorbed on mica (left image) and HOPG (right image) surfaces. By performing a proper rescaling of the scale bar according to the formula given in the main text, for both substrates the half-pitches appear to have the same physical length. In the central column, we compare the experimental values of the ratios $L(n, I)/L(2, I)$ for $n = 3, 4, 5$ (points) with the corresponding theoretical predictions (straight lines) for several values of ionic strength I in the case of both mica and HOPG substrates. Right: comparison between the experimental values of the half-pitches and theory after fit for fibrils adsorbed on mica and HOPG surfaces. In each case, all 20 experimental points were fitted simultaneously by tuning the parameters b and ϵ .

125 which is a remarkable parameter-free prediction. We leave to later in the manuscript the
 126 discussion on the explicit form of A , and turn first to the noteworthy predictive power of
 127 the $L(n_2, I)/L(n_1, I)$ expression in Eq. (4).

128 In the left panel of of Fig. 2, we show AFM mosaic images giving the half-pitch of
 129 multistranded β lg fibrils with $n = 2, 3, 4$ and 5 constitutive protofilaments without added
 130 salt (ionic strength of pH 2 pure water, i.e., 10 mM) acquired on mica (left image) and
 131 HOPG (right image) substrates. More details on sample preparation are given in the Meth-
 132 ods section of the Supplemental Material. The scale bar has identical physical length in
 133 each case, but indicates rescaled dimensions of $100 \text{ nm} \times (3n_2^2 - 7)^{1/2} / (3n_1^2 - 7)^{1/2}$ for each
 134 multistranded case, respectively, n_2 being the number of protofilaments composing the fibril
 135 under inspection and $n_1 = 2$ serving as a reference. After operating the above-mentioned
 136 rescaling, all the pitches become identical, consistently with our predictions. Because the
 137 predicted behavior is universal, i.e., independent of the physical parameters and in particu-
 138 lar of the ionic strength, in the left panel of Fig. 2 we further show the comparison between

139 theory and experiments at different ionic strengths (central column). We first note that,
 140 remarkably, the experimental data are indistinguishable when acquired on solutions incu-
 141 bated for either three weeks or over one year (see the Methods section of the Supplemental
 142 Material), confirming that the observed morphologies of the amyloid fibrils do correspond to
 143 thermodynamic equilibrium. Then, we plot $L(n, I)/L(2, I)$ for the sets of data for the two
 144 surfaces (data corresponding to the various values of n have been shifted in order to improve
 145 visualization), and horizontal lines correspond to our theory. The agreement between the-
 146 ory and experimental data is very good, given the total absence of fitting parameters in the
 147 predictions. Even more remarkably, as we show in Sec. S8 of the Supplemental Material,
 148 the parameter-free law is also in perfect agreement with the ratios extracted from other
 149 ribbonlike fibrils, made starting from lysozyme [30] and human amylin [31], thus strongly
 150 supporting the universality of this law. Moreover, we note that different packing arrange-
 151 ments are expected to result into new parameter-free laws (see Sec. S9), which points
 152 towards the existence of “universality classes” of amyloid architectures.

153 Having established the correctness and universality of our findings, we turn to the explicit
 154 form of A , which is related to the detailed form of the interaction energy. The elastic
 155 contribution to the energy is captured by Hookean springs between consecutive beads, with
 156 spring constant k_e . To estimate the electrostatic part of the energy, we use the Poisson-
 157 Boltzmann approximation, where the electrostatic interaction energy between two spherical
 158 surfaces of diameter b and charge ze at a minimum approach distance x , immersed in a
 159 solution of ionic strength I , can be written as [32]

$$U_I^{electrostatic} = \frac{1}{4}bZ(I)e^{-k(I)x}. \quad (5)$$

160 Here, $k(I)$ is the inverse of the Debye length, which describes how well the ions in solution
 161 screen the Coulomb repulsion, and $Z(I)$ is a function of the ionic strength and of several
 162 fundamental constants, such as the Avogadro number, the Boltzmann constant, etc. [see
 163 Sec. S4 of the Supplemental Material for the detailed functional forms of $k(I)$ and $Z(I)$],
 164 as well as the total charge of the single bead ze . The value of z is not known *a priori*
 165 from the experimental data. In this respect, physical arguments based on Manning theory
 166 of counterion condensation [33] point towards $z = 6$ as the most suitable value (see Secs.
 167 S6 and S7). Note that the interior of the fibrils is essentially dry, and that it is mostly
 168 through the exterior that fibrils interact via a screened electrostatic potential. Thus, Eq.

169 (5) approximates the screened electrostatic interaction between nearby portions of the fibril
 170 surface, in order to provide a coarse-grained picture of the twisting properties of fibrils.

171 The sum of the electrostatic and Hookean energies gives a formula for $U_I(x)$ which, by
 172 means of Eq. (3), provides the explicit dependence of the half-pitch L on the details of the
 173 system, which turns out to be (see Sec. S4 for the full derivation)

$$L(n, I) = \pi b \sqrt{\frac{3n^2 - 7}{10} \frac{k_e e^{k(I)b\epsilon}}{k(I)Z(I)}} (1 + \epsilon). \quad (6)$$

174 In Eq. (6), the terms k_e and ϵ are the only unknown variables, and thus play the role of
 175 fitting parameters, whose optimization leads to the curves reported in the right panel of
 176 Fig. 2. The final values of the parameters are $k_e = (0.39 \pm 0.03)$ N/m, $\epsilon = 0.96 \pm 0.05$
 177 for mica, and $k_e = (0.35 \pm 0.02)$ N/m, $\epsilon = 1.05 \pm 0.04$ in the case of HOPG. Note that
 178 for each substrate all 20 experimental data points are used simultaneously in the fit (i.e.,
 179 for each substrate a single pair of $k_e : \epsilon$ allows fitting simultaneously all 20 experimental
 180 observations). From the fitted value of k_e , it is possible to give an estimate of the torsional
 181 elastic properties of fibrils. In particular, apart from numerical prefactors which depend on
 182 n and ϵ (both of order unity), the shear modulus G is given by $G \sim k_e/b \sim 10^{-1}$ GPa, in
 183 agreement with previously reported experimental results [8]. Moreover, the fact that the
 184 best-fit values of the $k_e : \epsilon$ pair differ by 10% or less between the two substrates, which have
 185 very different surface energies, conclusively demonstrates that surface adsorption effects do
 186 not strongly affect the measured values of fibrils periodicity. These effects are relevant only
 187 at large values of ionic strength. Indeed, as already noticed in [29], for large I and n the fibrils
 188 appear as smashed on the surface due to adhesion forces. In Sec. S10 of the Supplemental
 189 Material, we consider a refined model where the interaction with the surface is explicitly
 190 taken into account. Within this model, we show for HOPG, where no additional electrostatic
 191 interactions play a role, that this allows us to further improve the accuracy of the model in
 192 the regime of high pitches (large I and n). The very good agreement between our theoretical
 193 predictions and the experimental points confirms that, in spite of its simplicity, our model
 194 has not only captured the essential mechanism ruling the mesoscopic structure of the fibrils,
 195 but it is also capable of describing the data quantitatively.

196 We have shown here that the trade-off between the competing energetic contributions
 197 of electrostatics and elasticity governs the mesoscopic architecture of amyloid fibrils. Our
 198 model quantitatively predicts the dependence of the pitch of the twist of the fibers upon the

199 number of protofilaments and on the physical parameters, and in doing so demonstrates the
200 existence of hitherto unknown universal, parameter-free features, bringing an unprecedented
201 new description on the physical mechanisms controlling amyloid fibrils self-assembly. More
202 generally, our results should apply whenever two different competing interactions, not neces-
203 sarily of elastic and electrostatic nature, destabilize the flat architecture of the ribbon, so to
204 give rise to twisted fibrils. From an even broader perspective, our findings suggest that there
205 might be a number of yet undiscovered universal laws governing several mesoscale features
206 of protein fibrillar aggregates.

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